

Equivalents of Certain Minimal Element Principles

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Abstract

In this article, by applying our 2023 Metatheorem in ordered fixed point theory, we obtain various Minimal Element Principles with their equivalent formulations to existence theorems on minimal elements, common fixed points, common stationary points, and others. Some known theorems and new ones appear in such equivalents. Consequently, dual versions of the Ekeland principle (1972-74), the Caristi theorem (1976, 1979), works of Bae-Park (1983), Takahashi (1991), Lin-Du (2008), Cobzaş (2022), and others are substantially strengthened.

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1. Introduction

Since the appearances of the Ekeland variational principle [7, 8] in 1972-74 and the Caristi fixed point theorem [5] in 1976, nearly one thousand works followed on their equivalents, generalizations, imitations, applications, and related topics. Many of them are related to new spaces extending complete metric spaces, new metrics or topologies on them, and new order relations extending the so-called Caristi order.

While the author was working on the same subject in 1985-2000, we found a Metatheorem on ordered fixed point theory. It claims that certain order theoretic maximal element statements are equivalent to theorems on fixed points of progressive maps, stationary points, common fixed points, common stationary points of families of maps or multimaps. Apparently, their dual forms to minimal element statements can be possible.

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After 22 years have passed, we began again to study our Metatheorem in [17] and applied its extended versions in several works in 2022 [18,19,21]. Recall that Brøndsted [3] in 1976 observed certain case that maximal elements are fixed points and that Jachymski [9] in 2003 studied when periodic points are same to fixed points. Recently, in 2022, we obtained extended versions of our Metatheorem with the Brøndsted-Jachymski Principle and applied them to various results related maximality and progressive maps [18-21]. Later, in the end of 2022, we obtained a more general version of them called the 2023 Metatheorem in [24]. However, their counterparts related minimality and anti-progressive maps are quite a few. We began such study in our recent article [25].

Motivated by these, in the present article, we obtain various forms of Minimal Element Principles and apply them to known or new works related to minimality. We are based on our 2023 Metatheorem, a prototype of Minimal Element Principles, and the Brøndsted-Jachymski Principle for the minimality. These are dual versions of the corresponding ones on the maximality.

This article is organized as follows: In Section 2, we introduce the Caristi fixed point theorem, the contents of Brøndsted [3] and Jachymski [9], and apply them to Zermelo fixed point theorem [17] and others. Section 3 devotes equivalent formulations the Caristi theorem by following our 2023 Metatheorem. In Section 4, known consequences of our main theorem and related results in [1, 2, 5, 7, 8, 16] are introduced.

2. Basic principle

Let (X, \preceq) be a *preordered set*; that is, X is a nonempty set and \preceq is reflexive and transitive.

From our 2023 Metatheorem in [24], we deduced the following prototype of Maximal (resp. Minimal) Element Principles in [25]:

Theorem 2.1. *Let (X, \preceq) be a preordered set and A be a nonempty subset of X . Then the following statements are equivalent:*

(α) *There exists a maximal (resp. minimal) element $v \in A$, that is, $v \not\prec w$ (resp. $w \not\prec v$) for any $w \in X \setminus \{v\}$.*

(β) *If \mathfrak{F} is a family of maps $f : A \rightarrow X$ such that, for any $x \in A$ with $x \neq f(x)$, there exists a $y \in X \setminus \{x\}$ satisfying $x \preceq y$ (resp. $y \preceq x$), then \mathfrak{F} has a common fixed element $v \in A$, that is, $v = f(v)$ for all $f \in \mathfrak{F}$.*

(γ) *If \mathfrak{F} is a family of maps $f : A \rightarrow X$ satisfying $x \preceq f(x)$ (resp. $f(x) \preceq x$) for all $x \in A$ with $x \neq f(x)$, then \mathfrak{F} has a common fixed element $v \in A$, that is, $v = f(v)$ for all $f \in \mathfrak{F}$.*

(δ) *Let \mathfrak{F} be a family of multimaps $F : A \multimap X$ such that, for any $x \in A \setminus F(x)$, there exists $y \in X \setminus \{x\}$ satisfying $x \preceq y$ (resp. $y \preceq x$). Then \mathfrak{F} has a common fixed element $v \in A$, that is, $v \in F(v)$ for all $F \in \mathfrak{F}$.*

(ϵ) *If \mathfrak{F} is a family of multimaps $F : A \multimap X$ such that $x \preceq y$ (resp. $y \preceq x$) holds for any $x \in A$ and any $y \in F(x) \setminus \{x\}$, then \mathfrak{F} has a common stationary element $v \in A$, that is, $\{v\} = F(v)$ for all $F \in \mathfrak{F}$.*

(ζ) *Let \mathfrak{F} be a family of multimaps $F : A \multimap X$ such that, for all $x \in A$ with $F(x) \neq \emptyset$, there exists $y \in X \setminus \{x\}$ such that $x \preceq y$ (resp. $y \preceq x$) holds. Then there exists $v \in A$ such that $F(v) = \emptyset$ for all $F \in \mathfrak{F}$.*

(η) *If Y is a subset of X such that, for each $x \in A \setminus Y$, there exists a $z \in X \setminus \{x\}$ satisfying $x \preceq z$ (resp. $z \preceq x$), then there exists a $v \in A \cap Y$.*

Remark 2.2. (1) Note that we claimed that (α) – (η) are equivalent in Theorem 2.1 and did not say that they are true. For a counter-example, consider the real line \mathbb{R} with the usual order.

(2) All the elements v 's in Theorem 2.1 are same as we have seen in the proof of Metatheorem in [24].

Let (X, \preceq) be a preordered set and $F : X \multimap X$ a multimap. For every $x \in X$, motivated by Jinlu Li [12], we denote

$$\begin{aligned} S_+F(x) &:= \{z \in X : u \preceq z \text{ for some } u \in F(x)\}, \\ S_-F(x) &:= \{z \in X : z \preceq u \text{ for some } u \in F(x)\}. \end{aligned}$$

Especially, we follow Cobzaş [3]: For the identity map $F = 1_X$ and $x \in X$, put

$$S_+(x) = \{z \in X : x \preceq z\}, \quad S_-(x) = \{z \in X : z \preceq x\}.$$

A partially ordered set (poset) is a preordered set having the anti-symmetry.

From Theorem 2.1, we have several variants:

Theorem 2.3. *Let (X, \preceq) be a partially ordered set, $F : X \multimap X$ a multimap, $x_0 \in X$ such that $A = (S_+F(x_0), \preceq)$ has an upper bound (resp. $A = (S_-F(x_0), \preceq)$ has a lower bound) $v \in A$.*

Then the equivalent statements $(\alpha) - (\eta)$ of Theorem 2.1 hold.

Proof. It suffices to show Theorem 2.1(α) holds: Since $z \preceq v$ for any $z \in A = S_+F(x_0)$, $u \preceq z$ for some $u \in F(x_0)$. Since $u \preceq z \preceq v$, we have $v \in S_+F(x_0)$. Hence v is a maximal element of A . \square

For the identity map $F = 1_X$, Theorem 2.3 reduces to the following:

Theorem 2.4. *Let (X, \preceq) be a partially ordered set, $x_0 \in X$ such that $A = (S_+(x_0), \preceq)$ has an upper bound (resp. $A = (S_-(x_0), \preceq)$ has a lower bound) $v \in A$.*

Then the equivalent statements $(\alpha) - (\eta)$ of Theorem 2.1 hold.

3. The Brøndsted-Jachymski Principle

For a preordered set (X, \preceq) , a selfmap $f : X \rightarrow X$ is said to be *progressive* if $x \preceq f(x)$ for all $x \in X$; and *anti-progressive* if $f(x) \preceq x$ for all $x \in X$. Such maps appear in (iv) of Theorems 2.1, 2.3, and 2.4.

Recently, motivated by Brøndsted [3], we adopted the following in Park [20]:

Brøndsted Principle. *Let (X, \preceq) be a preordered set and $f : X \rightarrow X$ be a progressive (resp. anti-progressive) map. Then a maximal (resp. minimal) element $v \in X$ is a fixed point of f .*

Note that this principle is just Theorem 2.1 $(\alpha) \implies (\gamma)$ with $X = A$.

Remark 3.1. We noticed that, in most applications of this principle for partially ordered sets (X, \preceq) , the existence of a maximal (resp. minimal) element is achieved by the upper (resp. lower) bound of a chain in (X, \preceq) as in Zorn's Lemma.

From now on $\text{Max}(\preceq)$ (resp. $\text{Min}(\preceq)$) denotes the set of maximal (resp. minimal) elements of the order \preceq , and $\text{Fix}(f)$ (resp. $\text{Per}(f)$) denotes the set of all fixed points (resp. periodic) points of a map $f : X \rightarrow X$, respectively.

The following was given by Jachymski [9, Proposition 1]:

Proposition 3.2. *Let (X, \preceq) be a partially ordered set and $f : X \rightarrow X$ be progressive. Then $\text{Per}(f) = \text{Fix}(f)$.*

This also holds for anti-progressive maps. Combining this with the Brøndsted Principle, we obtain the following [21]:

Brøndsted-Jachymski Principle. *Let (X, \preceq) be a partially ordered set and $f : X \rightarrow X$ be a progressive map. Then we have*

$$\text{Max}(\preceq) \subset \text{Fix}(f) = \text{Per}(f).$$

Similarly, if $f : X \rightarrow X$ is a anti-progressive map, then we have

$$\text{Min}(\preceq) \subset \text{Fix}(f) = \text{Per}(f).$$

This also follows from Theorem 2.1 for a partially ordered set $X = A$ with

(γ') *If $f : X \rightarrow X$ is a map such that $x \preceq f(x)$ (resp. $f(x) \preceq x$) for any $x \in X$, then f has a fixed and periodic element $v \in X$, that is, $v = f(v)$.*

Remark 3.3. Note that this gives a new proof of the Brøndsted-Jachymski Principle. This is not claiming the non-emptiness of the three sets.

4. Strengthening the Caristi theorem

A real-valued function $f : X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ on a topological space X is said to be *lower (resp. upper) semicontinuous* (l.s.c.) (resp. u.s.c.) whenever

$$\{x \in X : f(x) > r\} \quad (\text{resp. } \{x \in X : f(x) < r\})$$

is open for each $r \in \mathbb{R}$.

Recall the following celebrated theorem [4]:

Theorem 4.1. (Caristi) *Let (X, d) be a complete metric space and $f : X \rightarrow X$ be a map such that for all $x \in X$,*

$$(C_\varphi) \quad d(x, f(x)) \leq \varphi(x) - \varphi(f(x)),$$

where a function $\varphi : X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+$ is lower semicontinuous. Then f has a fixed point.

For the history of various proofs of the Caristi theorem, see Kirk [11].

A map satisfying (C_φ) is called a Caristi map. Now, Theorem 4.1 simply tells that *any Caristi map on a complete metric space has a fixed point.*

In Theorem 4.1, (X, d) is a partially ordered set by defining

$$x \preceq y \quad \text{iff} \quad d(x, y) \leq \varphi(x) - \varphi(y) \quad \text{for } x, y \in X.$$

A Caristi map f is progressive by defining $x \preceq f(x)$ if and only if (C_φ) holds for any $x \in X$.

Now the Caristi theorem is strengthened as follows:

Theorem 4.2. *Let (X, d) be a complete metric space and $f : X \rightarrow X$ be a Caristi map. Then*

$$\text{Max}(\preceq) \subset \text{Fix}(f) = \text{Per}(f) \neq \emptyset.$$

We obtained the following in [24]:

Theorem 4.3. *If (X, \preceq) is a partially ordered set such that every chain in (X, \preceq) has an upper bound and $f : X \rightarrow X$ is progressive, then we have*

$$\text{Max}(\preceq) \subset \text{Fix}(f) = \text{Per}(f) \neq \emptyset.$$

We also improved Zermelo's fixed point theorem given implicitly in 1908 [28] as follows in [24]:

Theorem 4.4. *Let (X, \preceq) be a partially ordered set in which each nonempty well-ordered subset has a least upper bound. Then every progressive map $f : X \rightarrow X$ has*

$$\text{Max}(\preceq) \subset \text{Fix}(f) = \text{Per}(f) \neq \emptyset.$$

5. Dual formulations of Caristi theorem

In our previous works [20, 25], we gave equivalent formulations of the Caristi theorem as follows:

Theorem 5.1. *Let (X, \preceq) be a partially ordered complete metric space, and a function $\varphi : X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+$ be lower semicontinuous such that*

$$x \preceq y \quad \text{iff} \quad d(x, y) \leq \varphi(x) - \varphi(y) \quad \text{for } x, y \in X.$$

Then the equivalent statements to the following hold:

(α) There exists a maximal element $v \in X$; that is, $v \not\leq w$ for any $w \in X \setminus \{v\}$.

($\gamma 1$) If $f : X \rightarrow X$ is a map such that $x \preceq f(x)$ for any $x \in X$, then f has a fixed element $v \in X$, that is, $v = f(v)$.

($\gamma 2$) If \mathfrak{F} is a family of maps $f : X \rightarrow X$ satisfying $x \preceq f(x)$ for all $x \in A$ with $x \neq f(x)$, then \mathfrak{F} has a common fixed element $v \in A$, that is, $v = f(v)$ for all $f \in \mathfrak{F}$.

Remark 5.2. Note that (α) is due to Ekeland [7, 8] and there the maximal element $v \in X$ in (α) is called a d -point. Recall that ($\gamma 1$) is given in Caristi [4]. The equivalence of (α) and ($\gamma 1$) is shown by Brézis-Browder [2]. Moreover, ($\gamma 2$) is given by Kasahara [10] and Siegel [26].

The following is a dual of Theorem 5.1; see also [24].

Theorem 5.3. Let (X, \preceq) be a partially ordered complete metric space, and a function $\varphi : X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+$ be upper semicontinuous and bounded above such that

$$y \preceq x \text{ iff } d(x, y) \leq \varphi(y) - \varphi(x) \text{ for } x, y \in X.$$

Then the following equivalent statements hold:

(α) There exists a minimal element $v \in X$; that is, $w \not\leq v$ for any $w \in X \setminus \{v\}$.

(β) If \mathfrak{F} is a family of maps $f : X \rightarrow X$ such that, for any $x \in X$ with $x \neq f(x)$, there exists a $y \in X \setminus \{x\}$ satisfying $y \preceq x$, then \mathfrak{F} has a common fixed element $v \in X$, that is, $v = f(v)$ for all $f \in \mathfrak{F}$.

(γ) If \mathfrak{F} is a family of maps $f : X \rightarrow X$ satisfying $f(x) \preceq x$ for all $x \in X$ with $x \neq f(x)$, then \mathfrak{F} has a common fixed element $v \in X$, that is, $v = f(v)$ for all $f \in \mathfrak{F}$.

(δ) If \mathfrak{F} is a family of multimaps $T : X \multimap X$ such that, for any $x \in X \setminus T(x)$, there exists $y \in X \setminus \{x\}$ satisfying $y \preceq x$, then \mathfrak{F} has a common fixed element $v \in X$, that is, $v \in T(v)$ for all $T \in \mathfrak{F}$.

(ϵ) If \mathfrak{F} is a family of multimaps $T : X \multimap X$ such that $y \preceq x$ holds for any $x \in A$ and any $y \in T(x) \setminus \{x\}$, then \mathfrak{F} has a common stationary element $v \in X$, that is, $\{v\} = T(v)$ for all $T \in \mathfrak{F}$.

(ζ) Let \mathfrak{F} be a family of multimaps $T : A \multimap X$ such that, for all $x \in A$ with $T(x) \neq \emptyset$, there exists $y \in X \setminus \{x\}$ satisfying $y \preceq x$ holds. Then there exists $v \in A$ such that $T(v) = \emptyset$ for all $T \in \mathfrak{F}$.

(η) If Y is a subset of X such that, for each $x \in X \setminus Y$, there exists a $z \in X \setminus \{x\}$ satisfying $z \preceq x$, then there exists an element $v \in Y$.

Proof. Clear from [20, Example 4.1] and Theorem 2.1. \square

Remark 5.4. (1) All the elements v 's in Theorem 5.3 are same as we can see in the proof of Metatheorem or Theorem 2.1.

(2) Theorem 5.3(γ) implies a dual to the Caristi fixed point theorem 4.2 and can be stated as follows:

Theorem 5.5. Let (X, \preceq) be a partially ordered complete metric space, and a function $\varphi : X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+$ be upper semicontinuous and bounded above such that

$$y \preceq x \text{ iff } d(x, y) \leq \varphi(y) - \varphi(x) \text{ for } x, y \in X.$$

Then every anti-progressive map $f : X \rightarrow X$ has

$$\text{Min}(\preceq) \subset \text{Fix}(f) = \text{Per}(f) \neq \emptyset.$$

6. Revisit to Bae-Park in 1983

By attempting to improve the Caristi fixed point theorem, Kirk has raised the question of whether f continues to have a fixed point if we replace $d(x, f(x))$ by $d(x, f(x))^p$ where $p > 1$ in the Caristi Theorem 4.1 (cf. Caristi [3J]).

In Bae-Park [1], after giving an example showing that Kirk's problem is not affirmative, it is recalled that the Caristi theorem and Theorem 5.1(α) are equivalent (Brézis-Browder [2]). This could be expressed more explicitly as follows by combining Theorems 5.1(α) and (γ); see [1, Theorem 1]:

Theorem 6.1. *Let (M, d) be a metric space, $\phi : M \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+$ an arbitrary function. Let \mathfrak{F} be the family of all selfmaps of M such that for each $x \in M$, we have*

$$(*) \quad d(x, f(x))^p \leq \phi(x) - \phi(f(x)) \text{ where } p > 0.$$

Then $v \in M$ is a common fixed point of \mathfrak{F} if and only if v satisfies $\phi(v) - \phi(x) < d(v, x)^p$ for every other point $x \in M$.

In Theorem 6.1, if M is complete and ϕ is lower semicontinuous, and if $0 < p < 1$, then ϕ has a point $v \in M$ satisfying $\phi(v) - \phi(x) < d(v, x)^p$ for each other point $x \in M$. This extends Ekeland's Theorem 5.1(α). To prove this, take a new metric ρ on M with $\rho(x, y) = d(x, y)/(1 + d(x, y))$ which is equivalent to the original metric d .

Moreover, in [1], we obtained the following [1, Theorem 2] and other related results.

Theorem 6.2. *Let (M, d) be a complete metric space and $\phi : M \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+$ a lower semicontinuous function. Let \mathfrak{F} be the family of all selfmaps of M such that for each $x \in M$, we have*

$$d(x, f(x))^p \leq \phi(x) - \phi(f(x)).$$

- (1) *If $0 < p \leq 1$, then \mathfrak{F} has a common fixed point.*
- (2) *If ϕ has a minimal d -point $v \in M$, then it is a common fixed point of \mathfrak{F} .*

This extends corresponding parts of Theorem 5.1.

Furthermore, Theorems 6.1 and 6.2 also can be reformulated by adopting our method in Theorem 3.1. For Theorem 6.2, we have the following:

Theorem 6.3. *Let (X, d) be a partially ordered complete metric space, a function $\varphi : X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+$ be lower semicontinuous, and $0 < p \leq 1$ such that*

$$x \preceq y \text{ iff } d(x, y)^p \leq \varphi(x) - \varphi(y) \text{ for } x, y \in X.$$

Then the equivalent statements in Theorem 5.1 hold. For example,

(α) *There exists a maximal element $v \in X$; that is, $v \not\preceq w$ (that is, $d(v, w)^p > \varphi(v) - \varphi(w)$) for any $w \in X \setminus \{v\}$.*

(γ) *Let \mathfrak{F} be the family of all selfmaps f of X such that for each $x \in M$, we have $x \preceq f(x)$ or*

$$d(x, f(x))^p \leq \phi(x) - \phi(f(x)).$$

Then \mathfrak{F} has a common fixed point $v \in X$.

Proof. Note that (γ) is just Theorem 6.2. From (γ), others (α) – (η) routinely follow. \square

Note that Theorem 6.3 for $p = 1$ reduces to Theorem 5.1 and that the dual version of them holds; that is, Theorem 5.2 with $d(x, y)^p$.

Moreover, by applying the Brøndsted-Jachymski Principle to Theorem 6.3, we have the following:

Theorem 6.4. *Under the hypothesis of Theorem 6.3, if $f : X \rightarrow X$ is progressive (that is, $d(x, f(x))^p \leq \phi(x) - \phi(f(x))$ for each $x \in X$), then we have*

$$\text{Max}(\preceq) \subset \text{Fix}(f) = \text{Per}(f) \neq \emptyset.$$

Similarly, if $f : X \rightarrow X$ is a anti-progressive map, then we have

$$\text{Min}(\preceq) \subset \text{Fix}(f) = \text{Per}(f) \neq \emptyset.$$

7. Application of Lin-Du in 2008

In 2008, Lin and Du [13] obtained some variants of Ekeland's variational principle (EVP) and their applications. In this section, we apply our Metatheorem to their results. They introduced the following:

Definition 7.1. [13] Let X be a t.v.s. A function $p : X \times X \rightarrow (-\infty, \infty]$ is called an ℓ -function if the following are satisfied:

- (L1) $p(x, x) \geq 0$ for all $x \in X$;
- (L2) for any $x \in X$, $p(x, \cdot)$ is convex;
- (L3) for any $y \in X$, $p(\cdot, y)$ is u.s.c.

Definition 7.2. [13] Let X be a t.v.s., $\phi : X \rightarrow (-\infty, \infty]$ and $p : X \times X \rightarrow (-\infty, \infty]$ be functions. We say that X satisfies (p, ϕ) -condition if there exist a nonempty compact subset K of X and a nonempty compact convex subset L of X such that for each $y \in X \setminus K$ there exists $z \in L$ such that $p(y, z) < \phi(y) - \phi(z)$.

Below, unless otherwise specified, they assume that X is a Hausdorff t.v.s., $\phi : X \rightarrow (-\infty, \infty]$ is a l.s.c. and convex function, $p : X \times X \rightarrow (-\infty, \infty]$ is an ℓ -function and X satisfies (p, ϕ) -condition.

In Section 4 of [13], Lin and Du established some existence theorems in a Hausdorff t.v.s. equipped with (p, ϕ) -condition and proved that these theorems are equivalent to Theorem 7.4 (their Theorem 4.2) below.

Here, they introduced a partial order on X as follows:

Definition 7.3. In Definition 7.2, they defined a partial order \preceq on X as follows:

$$x \preceq y \iff \phi(x) \leq \phi(y).$$

In [13], Lin and Du assumed the following condition several times. So we gave its name for simplicity as follows:

Lin-Du Condition. *Let X be a Hausdorff t.v.s. Let $\phi : X \rightarrow (-\infty, \infty]$ be a l.s.c. and convex function, $p : X \times X \rightarrow (-\infty, \infty]$ be an ℓ -function and $\varepsilon > 0$. Suppose that there exist a nonempty compact subset K of X and a nonempty compact convex subset L of X such that for each $y \in X \setminus K$ there exists $z \in L$ such that $\varepsilon p(y, z) < \phi(y) - \phi(z)$.*

The following results are variants of EVP for ℓ -functions in a Hausdorff t.v.s.

Theorem 7.4. [13] *Under the Lin-Du condition, there exists $v \in X$ such that $\varepsilon p(v, x) \geq \phi(v) - \phi(x)$ for all $x \in X$.*

Note that v is a maximal element in view of our Theorem 5.1 for \preceq on X .

The following theorem is a special case of a result of Lin et al. in 2002, see [13, Theorem 4.2]:

Theorem 7.5. [13] *If $\phi = 0$ in Theorem 7.4, then, there exists $v \in X$ such that $p(v, x) \geq 0$ for all $x \in X$.*

Remark 7.6. [13] It is easy to see that Theorems 7.4 and 7.5 are equivalent.

We derive the main theorem of this section:

Theorem 7.7. *Under the Lin-Du condition, the following equivalent nine statements hold:*

- (α) *There exists a maximal element $v \in X$, that is, $\varepsilon p(v, w) \geq \phi(v) - \phi(w)$. for any $w \in X \setminus \{v\}$.*
- (β) *If \mathfrak{F} is a family of maps $f : X \rightarrow X$ such that, for any $x \in X$ with $x \neq f(x)$, there exists a $y \in X \setminus \{x\}$ satisfying $\varepsilon p(x, y) < \phi(x) - \phi(y)$, then \mathfrak{F} has a common fixed element $v \in X$, that is, $v = f(v)$ for all $f \in \mathfrak{F}$.*
- (γ) *If \mathfrak{F} is a family of maps $f : X \rightarrow X$ satisfying $\varepsilon p(x, f(x)) < \phi(x) - \phi(f(x))$ for all $x \in X$ with $x \neq f(x)$, then \mathfrak{F} has a common fixed element $v \in X$, that is, $v = f(v)$ for all $f \in \mathfrak{F}$.*
- (δ) *If \mathfrak{F} is a family of multimaps $F : X \multimap X$ such that, for any $x \in X \setminus F(x)$ there exists $y \in X \setminus \{x\}$ satisfying $\varepsilon p(x, y) < \phi(x) - \phi(y)$, then \mathfrak{F} has a common fixed element $v \in X$, that is, $v \in F(v)$ for all $F \in \mathfrak{F}$.*
- (ϵ) *If \mathfrak{F} is a family of multimaps $F : X \multimap X$ such that $\varepsilon p(x, y) < \phi(x) - \phi(y)$ holds for any $x \in X$ and any $y \in F(x) \setminus \{x\}$, then \mathfrak{F} has a common stationary element $v \in X$, that is, $\{v\} = F(v)$ for all $F \in \mathfrak{F}$.*
- (ζ) *Let \mathfrak{F} be a family of multimaps $F : A \multimap X$ such that, for all $x \in A$ with $F(x) \neq \emptyset$, there exists $y \in X \setminus \{x\}$ such that $\varepsilon p(x, y) < \phi(x) - \phi(y)$. Then there exists $v \in A$ such that $F(v) = \emptyset$ for all $F \in \mathfrak{F}$.*
- (η) *If Y is a subset of X such that for each $x \in X \setminus Y$ there exists a $z \in X \setminus \{x\}$ such that $\varepsilon p(x, z) < \phi(x) - \phi(z)$, then there exists an element $v \in X \cap Y = Y$.*

Proof. (α) is a restatement of Theorem 7.4 [13, Theorem 4.2]. The equivalency of (α) – (η) follows from our Theorem 2.1. \square

From Theorem 7.7(α), (γ) and the Brøndsted-Jachymski Principle imply the following:

Theorem 7.8. *Under the Lin-Du condition, if $f : X \rightarrow X$ is progressive, then we have*

$$\text{Max}(\preceq) \subset \text{Fix}(f) = \text{Per}(f) \neq \emptyset.$$

From now on, we show that several theorems assuming the Lin-Du Condition in Section 4 of [13] follow from Theorem 7.7.

The following [13, Theorem 5.1] is a variant of Theorem 7.7(vii):

Theorem 7.9. [13] (Common fixed point theorem for a family of multivalued maps) *Let I be an index set. For each $i \in I$, let $T_i : X \multimap X$ be a multimap with nonempty values such that, for each $(i, x) \in I \times X$ with $x \notin T_i(x)$, there exists $y = y(x, i) \in X$ with $y \neq x$ satisfying $p(x, y) < f(x) - f(y)$. Then there exists $x_0 \in X$ such that $x_0 \in \bigcap_{i \in I} T_i(x_0)$, that is, $\{T_i\}_{i \in I}$ has a common fixed point in X .*

Moreover, the following [13, Theorem 5.2] is same to Theorem 7.7(γ):

Theorem 7.10. [13] (Common fixed point theorem for a family of single-valued maps) *Let I be an index set. For each $i \in I$, suppose that $T_i : X \rightarrow X$ is a map satisfying*

$$p(x, T_i x) < \phi(x) - \phi(T_i x)$$

for all $x \neq T_i(x)$. Then there exists $x_0 \in X$ such that $T_i(x_0) = x_0$ for all $i \in I$.

In [13], the equivalency of their Theorem 4.2, Theorems 5.1, 5.2 and the following Theorem 5.3 are shown:

Theorem 7.11. [13] (Maximal element theorem for a family of multimaps) *Let I be an index set. For each $i \in I$, let $T_i : X \multimap X$ be a multimap. Suppose that, for each $(x, i) \in X \times I$ with $T_i(x) \neq \emptyset$, there exists $y = y(x, i) \in X$ with $y \neq x$ such that $p(x, y) < f(x) - f(y)$. Then there exists $x_0 \in X$ such that $T_i(x_0) = \emptyset$ for all $i \in I$.*

8. Examples of Cobzaş

Our Metatheorem was originated from the Ekeland Principle which has equivalent forms like the Caristi fixed point theorem, Takahashi's minimization theorem, and many others. Our recent applications of Metatheorem to those theorems were given in [17], [22], [23], [24].

Recently, Cobzaş [6] in 2022 gave versions of Ekeland, Takahashi, Caristi Principles in preordered quasi-metric spaces, the equivalence to some completeness results for the underlying quasi-metric spaces.

For convenience, Cobzaş [6] formulated these three principles as follows:

Theorem 8.1. (Ekeland, Takahashi and Caristi principles) *Let (X, d) be a complete metric space and $\varphi : X \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \cup \{\infty\}$ a proper bounded below l.s.c. function. Then the following statements hold:*

[wEk] *There exists $z \in \text{dom } \varphi$ such that $\varphi(z) < \varphi(x) + d(x, z)$ for all $x \in X \setminus \{z\}$.*

[Tak] *If for every $x \in \text{dom } \varphi$ with $\varphi(x) > \inf \varphi(X)$ there exists an element $y \in \text{dom } \varphi \setminus \{x\}$ such that $\varphi(y) + d(x, y) \leq \varphi(x)$, then φ attains its minimum on X , i.e., there exists $z \in \text{dom } \varphi$ such that $\varphi(z) = \inf \varphi(X)$.*

[Car] *If the mapping $f : X \rightarrow X$ satisfies $d(f(x), x) + \varphi(f(x)) \leq \varphi(x)$ for all $x \in \text{dom } \varphi$, then f has a fixed point in $\text{dom } \varphi$, i.e., there exists $z \in \text{dom } \varphi$ such that $f(z) = z$.*

Here [wEk] means the weak Ekeland principle, [Tak] the Takahashi principle, and [Car] the Caristi fixed point theorem.

Motivated by Example 4.1 of [20], we derive the following; see also [24]:

Theorem 8.2. *Let (X, d) be a complete metric space and $\varphi : X \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \cup \{\infty\}$ a proper bounded below l.s.c. (resp. bounded above u.s.c.) function. Let $A = \text{dom } \varphi$.*

Then the following equivalent statements hold:

(α) *There exists a maximal (resp. minimal) element $v \in A$, that is,*

$$d(v, w) > \varphi(v) - \varphi(w) \text{ (resp. } d(v, w) > \varphi(w) - \varphi(v))$$

for any $w \in X \setminus \{v\}$. [wEk]

(β) *If \mathfrak{F} is a family of maps $f : A \rightarrow X$ such that, for any $x \in A$ with $x \neq f(x)$, there exists a $y \in X \setminus \{x\}$ satisfying*

$$d(x, y) \leq \varphi(x) - \varphi(y) \text{ (resp. } d(x, y) \leq \varphi(y) - \varphi(x)),$$

then \mathfrak{F} has a common fixed element $v \in A$, that is, $v = f(v)$ for all $f \in \mathfrak{F}$.

(γ) *If \mathfrak{F} is a family of maps $f : A \rightarrow X$ satisfying*

$$d(x, f(x)) \leq \varphi(x) - \varphi(f(x)) \text{ (resp. } d(x, f(x)) \leq \varphi(f(x)) - \varphi(x))$$

for all $x \in A \setminus \{f(x)\}$, then \mathfrak{F} has a common fixed element $v \in A$, that is, $v = f(v)$ for all $f \in \mathfrak{F}$.

(δ) *Let \mathfrak{F} be a family of multimaps $T : A \multimap X$ such that, for any $x \in A \setminus T(x)$, there exists $y \in X \setminus \{x\}$ satisfying*

$$d(x, y) \leq \varphi(x) - \varphi(y) \text{ (resp. } d(x, y) \leq \varphi(y) - \varphi(x)),$$

then \mathfrak{F} has a common fixed element $v \in A$, that is, $v \in T(v)$ for all $T \in \mathfrak{F}$.

(ϵ) *If \mathfrak{F} is a family of multimaps $T : A \multimap X$ such that*

$$d(x, y) \leq \varphi(x) - \varphi(y) \text{ (resp. } d(x, y) \leq \varphi(y) - \varphi(x))$$

holds for any $x \in A$ and any $y \in T(x) \setminus \{x\}$, then \mathfrak{F} has a common stationary element $v \in A$, that is, $\{v\} = T(v)$ for all $T \in \mathfrak{F}$.

(ζ) Let \mathfrak{F} be a family of multimaps $T : A \multimap X$ such that, for all $x \in A$ with $T(x) \neq \emptyset$, there exists $y \in X \setminus \{x\}$ satisfying

$$d(x, y) \leq \varphi(x) - \varphi(y) \quad (\text{resp. } d(x, y) \leq \varphi(y) - \varphi(x)).$$

Then there exists $v \in A$ such that $T(v) = \emptyset$ for all $T \in \mathfrak{F}$.

(η) If Y is a subset of X such that for each $x \in A \setminus Y$ there exists a $z \in X \setminus \{x\}$ satisfying

$$d(x, z) \leq \varphi(x) - \varphi(z) \quad (\text{resp. } d(x, z) \leq \varphi(z) - \varphi(x)),$$

then there exists a $v \in A \cap Y$.

In this theorem, note that “(α) \iff [wEk] with its dual form,” and “(γ') \iff [Car] with the first form” of the following particular form of γ :

(γ') If $f : A \rightarrow X$ is a map such that

$$d(x, f(x)) \leq \varphi(x) - \varphi(f(x)) \quad (\text{resp. } d(x, f(x)) \leq \varphi(f(x)) - \varphi(x))$$

for any $x \in A$, then f has a fixed element $v \in A$, that is, $v = f(v)$.

Moreover, we show that the single family case of “(ζ) \iff [Tak] with its dual form” as follows:

Theorem 8.3. *Theorem 8.2(ζ) implies the Takahashi principle and its dual form.*

Proof. For any $x \in A$ with $\varphi(x) > \inf \varphi(X)$,

$$T(x) = \{y \in X : \varphi(x) > \varphi(y)\}.$$

Suppose that for each $x \in A$, there exists $y \in A \setminus \{x\} \subset X \setminus \{x\}$ such that $d(x, y) \leq \varphi(x) - \varphi(y)$. Then, by (ζ) for the single family, we have $v \in A$ such that $T(v) = \emptyset$, that is, $\varphi(v) \leq \varphi(y)$ for all $y \in X$, or $\varphi(v) = \inf \varphi(X)$.

For the dual, $T(x) = \{y \in X : \varphi(y) > \varphi(x)\}$ works. \square

For some more details on Theorem 8.1, see Cobzaş (2022),

From Theorem 8.2(α), (γ) and the Brøndsted-Jachymski Principle, we have the following;

Theorem 8.4. *Let (X, d) be a complete metric space and $\varphi : X \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \cup \{\infty\}$ a proper bounded below l.s.c. (resp. bounded above u.s.c.) function. If $f : X \rightarrow X$ is a map such that*

$$d(x, f(x)) \leq \varphi(x) - \varphi(f(x)) \quad (\text{resp. } d(x, f(x)) \leq \varphi(f(x)) - \varphi(x))$$

for any $x \in X$. Then we have

$$\text{Max}(\preceq) = \text{Fix}(f) = \text{Per}(f) \neq \emptyset \quad (\text{resp. } \text{Min}(\preceq) = \text{Fix}(f) = \text{Per}(f) \neq \emptyset).$$

9. Conclusion

Since the Ekeland variational principle in 1972 and the Caristi fixed point theorem in 1976 appeared, more than one thousand related papers were published. Most of them are related to certain maximum principles in Nonlinear Analysis and belong to Ordered Fixed Point Theory [24].

In 1985-86, we obtained Metatheorem on equivalents of maximal theorems and various types of fixed point theorems. In 2022, we improved Metatheorem several times and its consequence like the Brøndsted-Jachymski principle. They were applied to a large number of existing or new results [17]–[23]. Finally, in the end of 2022, we obtained the reorganized 2023 Metatheorem and applied it to the new foundations of Ordered Fixed Point Theory [24].

The present article is based on certain minimum principles particular to the 2023 Metatheorem and applied them to several existing related results as a continuation to [25]. Further application would be possible and readers are encouraged to find further study on such topics.

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